

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: MORNA****FIRST NAME: EMMANUEL****PROGRAM CODE: DME****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 6%

The author used the following software: MS Word – Office 365 on Windows 10

List 5 to 7 key concepts with page numbers in text (then bold these terms in your RP):

1. Structure of academic essays (EUCLID 2024, 10-11)
2. Punctuation rules (EUCLID 2024, 16-23)
3. Style guide (EUCLID 2024, 41-42)
4. American versus British language style (EUCLID 2024, 25-32)
5. Avoiding plagiarism (EUCLID 2024, 33-39)

ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING FUNDAMENTALS

1) INTRODUCTION

After several years of contemplation, I finally got the courage to apply for a Doctor of Philosophy (Ph.D.) program last month with EUCLID University. To complete the program in good time, I promised myself to complete a course period every two weeks. Unfortunately, this is my third week of registering for my first course and starting ACA-401D (Period 1), which focuses on the fundamentals of academic writing. I have been caught up in a whirlwind of excitement, confusion, and worry. To overcome this, I have acquainted myself with the EUCLID protocols and guidelines, but as a beginner, there seems to be a lot to deal with.

I have taken the time to read the ACA-401/ACA-401D course pack revised by Prof. Laurent Cleenewerck and Dr. Kabiru Gulma. This course has revealed many academic essay writing basics I have taken for granted. It is a good foundation for my continued academic and professional growth. After juggling with my thoughts, combing through the materials provided, and my professional work, I have finally found the courage to put together this response paper as my first expected deliverable. The paper focuses on five significant concepts I find very insightful in the course pack for period one and the essential

tutorial videos. These include the structure of academic essays, punctuation rules, style guides, American versus British English language style and avoiding plagiarism.

2) STRUCTURE OF ACADEMIC ESSAYS

Academic writing is guided by structure. This helps to make one's ideas clear, shows the reader's comprehension, and can strengthen the arguments provided. For this reason, EUCLID (2024, 10) suggests a format that includes an introduction, body, and conclusion. This format is consistent with what I have seen and used for both written and speaking purposes. The introduction is where the writer prepares the readers and grabs their attention. It provides a quick preview of the main points of the essay. As a result, it is essential to have a short orientation or brief overview of the topic, including a thesis statement. Subsequently, all the main ideas to be discussed are presented logically (EUCLID 2024, 10).

The details of the main ideas are presented in the essay's body. This is where you present exposition and evidence to bolster your argument. This is also where you demonstrate your knowledge and grasp of the subject matter, supported by relevant examples and authoritative quotes. It consists of a series of paragraphs, which serve as building blocks (EUCLID 2024, 10). Each paragraph should do two things: first, make a relevant point, and second, back it up with evidence, quotation, argument, or example (Warburton 2006, 42). I have found that analyzing and interpreting this evidence is important, since it provides an opportunity to comment on its implications, significance and impact. This is an aspect most students find challenging and requires some level of critical thinking to get it correctly done.

The conclusion pulls everything together by re-summarizing all the main points, including possible implications and future direction for research, among others (EUCLID 2024, 10).

Although this format looks simple, writing the essay can be challenging. To overcome this, EUCLID (2024, 11) provides some tips for effective writing. These include starting early, ensuring that you refrain from trying to write an essay from beginning to end within a single study session, writing the introduction and conclusion after the body, revising your draft extensively, and proofreading it to address all grammatical errors.

3) PUNCTUATION RULES

Anyone who cares about grammar is sensitive to the use of punctuation. Wrong use of punctuation in a sentence can trigger a ghastly private emotional process similar to the stages of bereavement, though greatly accelerated (Truss 2004, 1). Appropriate punctuation is, therefore, crucial in academic essay writing. Punctuation helps readers to understand the message being delivered clearly.

To help students improve their essay writing, EUCLID (2024, 16-23) provides guidelines for the use of key punctuation marks, including apostrophes, brackets, colons and semicolons, commas, dashes and hyphens, ellipses, and quotation marks. I have used these punctuation marks over the years but found the explanations and some of the examples provided in this reading material regarding correct and wrong punctuation usage quite revealing. Generally, little punctuation should be used as necessary while retaining the sentence's meaning (EUCLID 2024, 16). For instance, I did not know that the different types of brackets, that is, round bracket (), square bracket [], angle bracket < >, and curly bracket { } are used differently in academic essay writing even though I am familiar with their mathematical usage. The round bracket adds additional information, date, and explanation, among others, to a sentence. An example is "Preheating the oven to 350°F (180 °C)." Conversely, the square bracket is used to enclose comments, corrections, references, or translations made by a subsequent author or editor. An example provided by EUCLID (2024, 17) is "This was quoted by Brown [1940, Chicago]." If this is the case, why is EUCLID using the round bracket for references instead of the square bracket?

In addition, in using a comma between items in a list, there is no comma between the penultimate item in a list and 'and'/'or'. For example, "I ate fish, bread, ice cream and spaghetti." I found this new because I have always added a comma before the 'and'/'or'. Even when I do not intentionally add the text, it will be underlined for me to correct. The comma is inserted in this position if it would help prevent confusion. A typical example provided in the EUCLID (2024, 19) is "I ate fish and chips, bread and jam, and ice cream."

This refresher in grammar and the implication for their wrong usage has triggered a renewed interest in learning more about punctuation. I have a presented copy of EUCLID (2024) on my desk as a reference material for all my writings now.

4) STYLE GUIDE

A style guide is a means of documenting your approach to some aspects of writing style that need consistency. Style guides are generally associated with certain types of writing like technical writing, commercial or business writing, journalism, and web copywriting (EUCLID 2024, 41). Reading through the materials, I now appreciate the importance of having a documented style guide, mainly if multiple people work on a single document. I have had the frustrating experience of spending several hours editing documents put together by different team members, each with his/her own style of writing. This is mainly due to using different spelling styles (American versus British English), font sizes, heading styles, among others. Ensuring consistency after the document has been written can be very challenging. Even as a person, I have noticed that I often write using a blend of different styles, which is inappropriate.

EUCLID (2024, 41-42) explains why a writer needs a particular style guide and provides critical components of a style guide to address this challenge. EUCLID recommends the Chicago Rules (Turabian) but is okay with other internationally recognized Rules. The Chicago Style Guide (2017, 3-6) provides formatting guidelines, including font, spacing, margins, alignment, indentation, page numbers, quotations (short

and long) among others. The style guide can consist of different aspects like preferred sentence lengths, manuscript layout, font usage, spelling (American versus British English), abbreviations, symbols, and structure. Other aspects are paragraph numbering and using headings and lists (EUCLID 2024, 41-42).

As a budding writer, the style guide is an invaluable tool to help me meet international standards and the needs of my customers as a Freelance Consultant.

5) AMERICAN VERSUS BRITISH LANGUAGE STYLE

Most of us often get confused about word differences between American and British English when writing. American and British English are both variants of World English. As such, they are more similar than different, especially with "educated" or "scientific" English. Most divergence can be ascribed to differing national histories and cultural development and the way in which the two national variants have changed correspondingly (EUCLID 2024, 25). Knowing the similarities and subtle differences between standard American English (SAE) and standard British English (SBE) is vital for a budding writer. Although both variants are accepted in technical and professional writing, as long as one remains consistent throughout the document, EUCLID recommends using SAE.

EUCLID 2024 (25-32) explains the different categories between SAE and SBE. Key among these is different pronunciation, although same spelling; different spelling, although same pronunciation; same term, different but similar spelling and pronunciation; grammar, syntax, punctuation, general usage; periods, commas, and quotation marks; punctuation with business (formal) vs. social (informal) letters; and so forth.

What was striking for me is the use of periods, commas, and quotation marks. For instance, SBE uses inverted commas for quotes such as 'The boy kicked the ball.' While SAE uses quotation marks, "The boy kicked the ball." (EUCLID 2024, 31). I noticed that the differences I always saw in writings were based on language style. Also, I found the use of punctuation with business (formal) versus social (informal) letters. For example, Dear Mr Smith, (SBE) versus Dear Mr. Smith: (SAE). The notable difference is SBE "Mr" versus the SAE "Mr." I have noticed that what we have been using is a blend of SAE and SBE, particularly "Dear Mr. Smith," in formal writing.

Consistent with the choice of language style in essay writing, therefore, cannot be over-emphasized.

6) AVOIDING PLAGIARISM

Plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information. For instance, taking someone else's words or ideas, such as quoting, paraphrasing, copying, and pasting from the internet, and not giving credit to the author. Having someone write a paper for you and then putting your name on it and

giving it to your professor would be plagiarism (EUCLID 2024, 34). Plagiarism can cause a student to be suspended or expelled. Some people have had their professional careers crumbled due to plagiarism allegations. Hence, it is important to know how to avoid it in order not to fall prey to it. To assist students to avoid plagiarism and ensure originality in their academic and professional writing, EUCLID 2024 (33-39) provides guidelines for properly citing authors or sources that have provided the information used.

One of the forms of citation is the *In-Text Citation*. Some of the more common things this method is used to cite are quotations and paraphrases. An example provided in EUCLID (2024, 24) is “Before 1984, footnotes and endnotes were used in research reports. In certain instances, this form of documentation is still correct” (Gerson and Gerson 143).’ However, I find this citation incomplete based on EUCLID’s recommended style, which includes the year of publication.

A few tips about quotations noteworthy in EUCLID (2024, 26) include limiting the use of quotations. Too many quotations do not make the work original. Also, use quotations when there is powerful language in the quote that emphasizes the meaning very well. Finally, use quotations when an authority figure says something that can help you persuade the reader.

7) CONCLUSION

Reading the ACA-401D period one-course pack and other relevant materials has been enriching. I have noted many nuances in the English language and essay writing, mainly using an organized and well-structured format for academic essay writing, following standard punctuation rules, and having a style guide. The others include appreciating the similarities and subtle differences in American versus British English language style and ensuring consistency in their usage and avoiding plagiarism to demonstrate the originality of your work.

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